

Charge and Stability of Colloids. Part XXIX. Effect of Non-electrolytes on the Antagonism of Ions in the Coagulation of Copper Ferrocyanide Sol

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Copper ferrocyanide sol has been sensitised in presence of non-electrolytes, such as dioxane, propanol² and dimethylformamide, using KCl, $MnCl_2$, and $CrCl_3$ as coagulators. The extent of sensitisation is greater in presence of non-electrolytes of low dielectric constant. The effect of the above non-electrolytes on the ionic antagonism of ions has been studied and it is generally observed that greater the dielectric constant of the non-electrolytes, the greater is the increase in the ionic antagonism for a particular pair of electrolyte mixture as compared to that in pure aqueous media.

Sen¹ observed that the precipitation values of KCl or $BaCl_2$ increased in presence of $K_4[Fe(CN)_6]$. Mukherjee and Ghosh² found a similar behaviour with the mixtures of sodium benzoate and sodium chloride on As_2S_3 sol. Sen's observations were confirmed and extended by Weiser³ using a highly purified copper ferrocyanide sol.

Pochhali and Mukherjee⁴ have studied the effect of non-electrolytes, i.e., CH_3OH , C_2H_5OH , sucrose, glycerol, and glycol, on the ionic antagonism of KCl and $BaCl_2$, while coagulating As_2S_3 sol. It has been found that the non-electrolytes, which stabilise the sol, increase the antagonism and those, which sensitise the sol, decrease it.

The non-electrolytes of low dielectric constants are found to sensitise the sol to a greater extent. The change in the dielectric constant on addition of non-electrolyte is certainly an influencing factor, but it alone is not sufficient to explain the facts observed⁵. An attempt has been made in this communication to explain the role of ionic antagonism in presence of non-electrolytes.

EXPERIMENTAL

Copper ferrocyanide sol was prepared by the method of Bcg⁶. The coagulating values were determined by taking 5 ml of sol in one test tube and in another, suitable amount of electrolyte and non-electrolyte mixture was made to 5 ml with distilled water. The contents of the two test tubes were mixed rapidly several times and placed inside an air bath, adjust-

1. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, **29**, 517; this *Journal*, 1926, **3**, 81.
2. This *Journal*, 1924, **1**, 213.
3. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, **30**, 1531; cf. Chatterjee, this *Journal*, 1935, **12**, 671.
4. This *Journal*, 1956, **33**, 201.
5. Lachs and Chwalinsky, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1932, **A159**, 172.
6. *Kolloid Z.*, 1957, **153**, 164.

ed at 30°. In every case the total volume was 10 ml. After one hour, the light from a single filament lamp was allowed to pass through a layer of definite thickness of coagulating mixture, placed at a constant distance, for a short interval of time. The light intensity was kept constant by passing a definite current and the disappearance of sharp outline of the filament was then noted.

The system studied was copper ferrocyanide sol with the pairs of electrolytes, viz., KCl-MnCl₂, KCl-CrCl₃, and MnCl₂-CrCl₃, and non-electrolytes: dioxane, propanol^a, dimethylformamide. The same sol was used throughout the investigation.

TABLE I

Coagulating conc.. of KCl, MnCl₂ and CrCl₃ (mM/litres).
Sol=3.136 g./litre.

%Non-electrolytes.	Dioxane.			Propanol ^a .			Dimethylformamide.		
	KCl.	MnCl ₂ .	CrCl ₃ .	KCl.	MnCl ₂ .	CrCl ₃ .	KCl.	MnCl ₂ .	CrCl ₃ .
0	26.000	0.300	0.100	26.000	0.300	0.100	26.000	0.300	0.100
5	17.000	0.188	0.106	18.000	0.212	0.134	..	..	..
10	9.500	0.128	0.058	10.000	0.188	0.100	17.000	0.220	0.150
20	..	..	..	..	..	..	15.000	0.188	0.140

TABLE II

Maximum or minimum total percentage of coagulating concentration with pair of electrolytes.

% Non-electrolyte mixed.	Total % coagulating concentration.		
	Min for KCl-MnCl ₂ .	Max. for KCl-CrCl ₃ .	Max. for MnCl ₂ -CrCl ₃ .
Non-electrolytes(%)	79	104	108
5% Dioxane	84	115	109
10% ..	81	109	105
10% Dimethylformamide	90	124	114
20% ..	93	110	116
5% Propanol ^a	85	105	106
10% ..	73	113	93

DISCUSSION

The coagulating concentrations of the electrolytes, viz, KCl, MnCl₂, and CrCl₃, are always lower in presence of non-electrolytes, e.g., dioxane, propanol^a, and dimethylformamide, than in the pure aqueous media. The lowering of the coagulating concentration or sensitisation of the sol depends on the lowering of the dielectric constant.

In pure aqueous media as well as in presence of non-electrolytes, the antagonistic action is negative for KCl-MnCl₂ and positive for KCl-CrCl₃ and MnCl₂-CrCl₃ electrolyte

mixtures (Table II). An explanation similar to that of Hazel⁷ can easily account for this behaviour of the sol with the above-mentioned sets of electrolytes. Lowering of coagulating concentration of $MnCl_2$ in presence of KCl may be attributed to the decrease in the stability of the sol, which probably occurs due to the compression of the double layer. The increase in coagulation values of $CrCl_3$ in presence of $MnCl_2$ and KCl can be explained owing to the positive antagonistic effect of ions. The extent of increase in the total percentage of coagulating concentration of the pair of electrolytes is greater in presence of non-electrolytes of high dielectric constant than in pure aqueous media (Table II). Since dimethylformamide has the highest dielectric constant, *i. e.*, 36.7 at 20°, among all the three non-electrolytes mentioned above, it should have maximum ionic antagonism. This is in conformity with our observations. From these results we can conclude that greater the dielectric constant of the non-electrolyte, the less will be sensitisation effect and consequently the ionic antagonism will be greater as compared to water.

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